

Recommended citation: Ritzen, R. G. P. (2018). Dynamic Behaviour of Coupled Systems A new course for second year's engineering students on modelling and simulation techniques in Matlab SIMSCAPE for describing dynamic behaviour of complex systems. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1167-1174). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672819.

Dynamic Behaviour of Coupled Systems

A new course for second year's engineering students on modelling and simulation techniques in Matlab SIMSCAPE for describing dynamic behaviour of complex systems

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Conference Key Areas: curriculum development, engineering skills, discipline-specific teaching and learning

Keywords: dynamic systems, modelling and simulation, Matlab Simscape, design challenges

INTRODUCTION

In modern design assignments engineers need to take an integrated approach during which the choice of materials, statics, dynamic behaviour and thermal aspects need to be taken into consideration. By the introduction of a redesigned curriculum for Mechanical Engineering at Fontys University of Applied Science a new course is introduced in the second year in which students will learn, using a predefined design case, how to take a system wide approach by taking mechanics and thermal and material aspects into account. Modern software tools and system design tools will be used to iteratively come to an optimal design solution.

Students work on several assignments during which knowledge on different subjects such as Matlab Simscape/Simulink, working in the frequency domain, designing for statics, dynamics and thermal behaviour will be explored. In the end the student will be able to use these elements combined in order to come to an integrated optimized system model and design solution of a given design case. The students present their

results in a detailed design report explaining all the steps taken to come to their optimized solution.

At Fontys University of Applied Science, the V-cycle (see *Fig. 1*) is an often used methodology in product development. The system wide approach, aimed for in this new course might become very useful, especially in the concept phase of the V-cycle, in future projects and even in professional life. [1,2] That's why the introduction of such a course is widely supported by teachers, members of the board of recommendation and companies in and around Eindhoven.

Fig. 1 A schematic representation of the V-cycle

In the first version of the new course in the previous academic year, students worked on designing a wingbox for an airplane wing by studying the effect of material choice and thickness on several aspects of the behaviour the wing. The results and experiences of teachers and students on this approach of system design are presented in this paper. A system model obtained by the students for this design case shows knowledge on fundamental engineering skills, student's creativity and enthusiasm for the approach on design thinking. Based on first experiences, a list of recommendations and future improvements for the course is formulated.

1 COURSE CONTENT

Groups of 2 students work on several assignments during which knowledge on different subjects such as Matlab Simscape, working in the frequency domain, designing for statics, dynamics and thermal behaviour will be explored. In the end the student will be able to use these elements combined in order to come to an integrated optimized system model and design solution of a given or chosen design case.

1.1 Learning objectives

In the development of the course, all different disciplines within the Mechanical Engineering department are asked to come up with their discipline specific wishes for such a course. Combining and summarizing all the input, resulted in a list of learning objectives as a starting point:

1. From a given design problem, the student is able to identify different design aspects and translate these aspects into design questions
2. The student is able to translate the design questions into an integral simplified system model(s)
3. The student has knowledge of working in the frequency domain and is able to use tools (such as Fast Fourier Transformation and/or Laplace transformations in order to predict the behaviour of a design)
4. The student is able to use appropriate simulation tools in order to translate the system model into a computer model that can be used to simulate and define design parameters
5. The student is able to make an integral optimized system design using the system and computer models.
6. The student is able to describe and summarize all design aspects into a professional report.

The pre knowledge required for the course is first years theory on statics, mechanics of materials, thermodynamics and practice on mathematical modelling in Matlab Simulink.

1.2 The design challenge

The students are asked to design the wingbox of an airplane wing using a systems based approach, meaning that they need to optimize for static, dynamic and thermodynamic (optional) requirements. For the sake of simplicity, the geometry (i.e. internal chord lengths, length of the of the wingbox, weight of the engine, etc., see Fig. 2) is already given to the students as a starting point for their design.

Fig. 2 Schematic representation of the wing, the wing box, the position of the engine and all typical length scales.

The wing structure must be strong enough in order to withstand the various loads which act on the wing. It should also meet stiffness requirements in order to dampen the vibrations as subtly as possible which might be caused by the dynamic loads during flight operations, for instance: a wind gust or a turbulence. In addition to the information mentioned above, the wing structure must also meet weight requirements in order to keep the flying costs at a reasonable level.

The design challenge gives freedom to optimize two characteristic design parameters in order to meet the above requirements: the *panel thickness* of the wingbox and the *material* of which the wingbox is made. [3]

1.3 Course contents

The first version of the course consists of three parts:

1. *The static design.* Students use their knowledge from first year's mechanics classes to study the static properties of the wing. They draw a free body diagram (FBD) and make plots of the bending moment, the shear forces, the normal stresses and shear stresses in order to determine where on the wingbox the maximum stresses act. This information is used to optimize for the panel thickness and material choice such that the wingbox can withstand the maximum stresses (taking into account a 1.5 safety factor) and the maximum deflection is calculated for the obtained design.
2. *Exercises in Matlab.* In a few basic exercises students get a first impression on building *physical* models using Matlab Simscape. The students learned how to build *mathematical* models based on differential equations in Matlab Simulink in a first years course on modelling and simulation. By adding Matlab Simscape to their skills, it offers opportunities to build models for more complex systems than they were used to so far. The basic exercises cover a model for a mass-spring-damper system, a double pendulum and an introduction and exercise on Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)
3. *The dynamical model.* A lumped parameter model for the wingbox is built in Matlab Simscape. The students make their own choices on how to set up the model using the standard building blocks available in Matlab Simscape (Multibody). In practice, it results approximating the wingbox by several solids connected by torsional springs. Based on the panel thickness and material properties obtained in the static design, students should be able to calculate spring constants and approximated damping constants. Once the lift force is added to the wingbox model, students can draw conclusions from graphs on the dynamic motion of the wing and elaborate on typical frequencies that occur according to the FFT analysis.

Note: the thermodynamical part is skipped in this first version of the course to prevent from creating an overload of work for students within the available hours (in total 3 ECTS) and to step by step develop the course instead of everything at once.

2 RESULTS AND EXPERIENCES

The course has had its first year in practise and some of the results are shown here.

2.1 A student's example

As an example, in *Fig. 3* a graphical three-dimensional representation of a model build in Matlab Simscape by two students is given. As a material they opt for an alunium alloy, 2014 UNS A92014, and a panel thickness of 11.5 mm. [4]

Fig. 3 A lumped model build in Matlab Simscape by students to study the dynamic behaviour of the wingbox.

These students chose to build up their model from 35 solids, each one connected with the previous one by a torsional spring. In *Fig. 4* a snapshot of a part of the model in Matlab Simscape is shown. *Part 1* represents a single solid with the mass of the solid and the typical dimensions as input parameters. The *Revolute Joint* represents the torsional spring with a calculated spring constant and an approximated damping constant as input parameters. It outputs (optional) the relative angle and angular acceleration, which can be plotted. Attached to the solid *Part 1* is an *External Force and Torque*, which represents the lift force that acts on the wing. The lift force is calculated within the Matlab Workspace using a script file. The connection points *Conn1* and *Conn2* connects the solid to his neighbouring ones. Some of the result of running the Simscape model can be found in *Fig. 5*. In the report, the students have reflected on the effect of slightly changing spring constants on the resonance frequency and the influence of adding a random noise signal to the lift force (simulating the effect of turbulence).

Fig. 4 A snapshot of the building blocks in Matlab Simscape used to model a single solid of the wingbox.

Fig. 5 Simulation results from Matlab Simscape (i) The deflection of the tip of the wing with respect to the fuselage (ii) the relative angles between solids at each 5 m of the wing (iii) the FFT corresponding to the relative angles showing a resonance frequency of 3.8 Hz

2.2 The results

In *Table 1* the passing grades are shown for the first generation of students that have followed the new course. The course was taught to three classes of which two were in Dutch and one in English (international students). In the end, 76% of the students passed the course. Remarkably, none of the international students passed for the regular exam. From evaluation with students it appeared that this was due to miss-communication, multiple deadlines at the same time and poor translation of the course manual. For the second attempt extra guidance is offered for these students.

Overall, the reports delivered by the students show great creativity and usefulness of such a design tool. The passing grade in the end is satisfactory and gives reason to continue the course and develop it even more.

Table 1 Passing grades (per class and total) for first attempt (regular exam) and second attempt (resit exam)

	NUMBER OF STUDENTS	FIRST TIME PASS (#)	FIRST TIME PASS (%)	SECOND TIME PASS (#)	SECOND TIME PASS (%)	TOTAL PASS (%)
CLASS 1 (dutch)	39	27	69	3	8	77
CLASS 2 (dutch)	34	13	38	15	44	82
CLASS 3 (english)	25	0	0	16	64	64
TOTAL	98	40	41	34	35	76

3 FUTURE ADAPTATIONS

Based on the first experiences with this new course and feedback we received from both teachers and students, a few adaptations and additions are formulated.

1. *Changing the order the main parts of the course.* The course started, just after the summer break, with calculations by hand on the static behaviour of the wingbox. The students find problems to recall on how to perform these calculations, getting back in working mode again after the holidays and consequently create a certain backlog. The result is a motivation drop immediately at the beginning of the course. Next time, the course starts with the basic introduction exercises into Matlab Simscape to make the first few weeks more easy going and fun.

2. *Simplifying the Matlab scripts.* The Matlab scripts provided to the students contain a lot of options to test and verify the influence of the design parameters on the dynamic behaviour of the wingbox. Although students are experienced in using Matlab Simulink, there's hardly now knowledge on script writing in Matlab. This makes it hard for them to understand what is written down in the script. Therefore, stripping down the scripts to a minimal level is essential.
3. *Adding a thermal component to the design challenge.* The first version of the course only focusses, for practical reasoning, on the static and dynamic components of the design challenge. The thermal component is added in the newer version. This is done by introducing the concept of deicing of a wing to the problem. For deicing, heat from the engine is blown under high pressure to the leading edge of the wing to provide ice from arising on the wing. This is typically affected by the choice of material and the thickness of the wingbox panels and therefor a good addition to this design challenge.
4. *Adding the option of a two degrees of freedom motion.* The dynamic motion of the wing is now restricted to motion in vertical direction, the so called plunge of the wing. For students who need some more challenge, also rotation about the elastic axis of the wing might be added. This is referred to as the pitch motion of the wing. The combination of pitch and plunge is often studied in the phenomenon flutter and so this extra option adds some more real issues to the actual design challenge.

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